

Amperometric biosensor for dust estimation : Comparison of enzyme electrode and dual-step potential electrode

Priyabrata Sarkar

Department of Polymer Science and Technology, University of Calcutta, 92, A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009, India

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The proposed methods of detection of dust exploit the fact that dust particles contain proteins from various sources to evolve easy-to-use sensors to estimate house-dust, dust in working place and in laboratory. The first of these methods utilised the enzyme protease, which converts proteins present in the dust to amino acids, which in turn is detected by an enzyme sensor. The second method is based on the reaction of bromine with protein on working electrode of the sensor.

Dust pollution has remained a serious problem and possesses a potential threat to mankind. It is useful to know whether an environment is harmful to health so that precautions can be taken to avoid unhealthy conditions, once it is tested for a dust level. Though, at this stage, it is very difficult to assess quantitative difference between various allergens present in the dust, an overall idea of the dust level might be obtained by determining the protein content in the dust.

Enzyme electrode : The efficiency of this electrode rests on the construction of the amino acid electrode. Individual or bulk amino acid levels are commonly measured through direct reaction with colourimetric agents, such as ninhydrin¹ or via redox dyes². Pre- or post-column analyte derivatisation is usual since most amino acids are not amenable to direct optical or electrochemical detection.

Biosensors, immobilising amino acid-specific enzymes coupled to electrochemical transducers have also been developed for direct, rapid measurement of amino acids in solution. Typically, amino acid analytes are enzymatically oxidised using a specific or broad-spectrum amino acid oxidase (AAO) (Scheme 1). The re-oxidation of reduced elec-

tron acceptor (mediator) is measured amperometrically at a working electrode and the resultant current-increase measured³⁻⁵. Stability has been a critical issue with many electrochemical amino acid sensors with significant decrease in

response after 1 month of preparation⁴⁻⁶. Both L- and D-amino acids have been immobilised on a polyethyleneamine-modified rhodinised carbon paste electrode⁷. This electrode exhibited good stability up to 2 months and could detect almost all commonly available L- and D- amino acids. Protease has been immobilised on immunodyne ABC membrane. The membrane was held firmly on the working electrode. The membranes soaked with requisite buffer were used to wipe out dust directly from the surface. The protein in dust reacted with protease to release free amino acid, which was subsequently detected by amino acid biosensor.

Dual-step potential electrode : Lack of electrochemically active species in proteins poses a problem for their detection by electrochemical means. One major problem of measuring protein and large amino acids is their restricted diffusion to the electrode surface and the slow rate of electron transfer. Fung and Mo⁸ used a serial dual electrode detector to measure several amino acids and proteins in a flow injection system. They used two electrodes in a continuous flow system. Also the system was limited to only laboratory measurements. The basic principles used in their system have been utilised by the present author⁹ on a screen-printed *single* electrode to make the sensor more useful, practical and suitable for on-site measurement. Bromine, because of its small size, can penetrate into the large molecules and react quickly with the double bond present in most of the amino acids and proteins. This principle was exploited in our electrode using a two-step potential across the working electrode for a stipulated length of time; bromine was generated at a higher voltage on the working electrode and consumed and detected at a lower voltage on the same electrode.

Results and Discussion

The real time responses for house dust with enzyme electrode and dual-step potential electrode are compared in

Fig. 1. The dual potential electrode was found to be more sensitive than the enzyme electrode. The reason might be due to the faster reaction of bromine with protein than the hydrolysis of protein by enzyme. The linear range, however, was higher for the enzyme electrode (up to 4 mg) than that of the dual potential electrode (0.5 mg). Tests were also conducted with equal quantity (2 mg) of dust from various places, i.e. house, office and laboratory. Dust from labora-

Fig. 1. Comparison of the response of enzyme electrode and dual-step potential electrode for different amount of dusts ($r = 3$, SD = error bars, values corrected for base line response)

tory gave the highest response whereas house and office dusts gave considerably lower but similar response. The high response of dust in biochemical laboratories might be attributed to its free amino acids and pure protein content. The calibration curves were constructed using standard protein

(BSA) for both the electrodes and protein content was calculated and compared with BCA protein assay kit (Pierce, Rockford, U.S.A.) (Table 1). The sample for the kit was prepared by keeping the dust sample in phosphate buffer overnight and filtering the suspension. The enzyme electrode underestimated the protein content in dust and dual potential electrode overestimated it. However, there was a possibility of presence of other interfering substances in the

Table 1. Comparison of performance of enzyme electrode and dual-step potential electrode on some proteins and house dust

Sample	Enzyme electrode			Dual potential electrode			BCA assay protein mg/ml
	Response nA	CV %	Protein mg/ml	Response nA	CV %	Protein mg/ml	
House dust (0.5 mg)	150	7.5	0.45	750	11	1.19	0.75
Milk ^a	626	6.5	18.7	1352	5.7	21.6	19.7
Fruit juice ^b	369	7.8	5.5	957	13.4	7.6	6.6
Urine ^b	100	11.2	1.5	188	10.4	1.5	0.5

^a1:10 dilution ^b1:5 dilution

dust which could not be eliminated in all the three procedures. The results using electrochemical approach on some other real samples compared very well (except urine) with the standard procedure (BCA). The presence of cysteine, a self-electroactive amino acid in urine was responsible for the difference. Table 2 gives a comparative study of the overall performance of all the three methods. The electrochemical methods certainly have several advantages over

Table 2. Comparison of the amperometric tri-enzyme sensor, dual-step potential electrode and standard BCA method for measurement of protein in house dust

Factor	Enzyme electrode	Dual-step potential electrode	Photometric method
Assay procedure	Simple, sample directly applied to electrode	Simple, sample directly applied to electrode	Complex, many handling steps
Linear range, mg	0.2-4	0-0.5	0-2
Limit of detection, mg	0.2	0.02	0.3
Time, min	4	4	60
Stability	<2 months	>1 year	-
Costs	Low labour and reagent costs	Only fabrication costs, no reagent costs	High labour costs, many reagents
Limitations	40% activity loss in two months	Change in potential needs costly hand held meters	Non portable system
Merits	Cheap, rapid, portable	Cheapest, rapid, portable	Stable

the conventional procedure and thus prove useful in certain applications.

Conclusions : The proposed sensors are inexpensive, easy-to-use and exhibited excellent performance in detection of dust level. The screen-printed amino acid electrodes and immunodyne ABC membrane provide a simple, sensitive indication of dust level. In the enzyme sensor, the inherent problem of stability remains. However, in the dual-step potential electrode, this is overcome. The latter also offers an improvement on the sensitivity of detection. These sensors might be useful in detection of health hazard in an apparently clean environment. The amount of dust per unit area could be a standard measurement criterion. Both the sensors can replace the conventional method for detection of dust and protein in many real samples as revealed from

taining 1% (w/v) PEI. However, the WE for the dual potential electrode was made from only MCA4A an HEC in the above proportion. The material for the reference electrode was 15% silver chloride in silver paste (MCA) for both types. To protect the underlying basal tracks from solution, an epoxy-based protective coating ink 242-SB (Agmet ESL Ltd. U.K.) was deposited over areas of the electrodes that were not exposed to sample, leaving tracks exposed at the proximal end in order to make electrical connection with the instrument.

Electrode construction : A DEK 248 screen printer (DEK Printing Machines, U.K.) was used to print the electrodes. The sensor consisted of a working electrode, reference electrode and counter electrode. Fig. 2 represents four different types of screens used for the printing of the elec-

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of screens used to print electrode : (a) basal track, (b) reference electrode, (c) working electrode and (d) polymer coating; black area represents screen opening.

Table 2. Though the sensors are suitable to indicate overall cleanliness, there is a need to fix a threshold value of the dust above which it is hazardous to health. The detection should also be more specific for common allergens. Work along this line is in progress.

Experimental

Immunodyne ABC membrane, 3 μm (Pall Europe Limited), protease (EC 3.4.24.31 from *Streptomyces griseus* : 5.2 units/mg), L-AAO (EC 1.4.3.2 extracted from venom of *Crotalus adamateus* : 0.31 units/mg and D-AAO (EC 1.4.3.3 from porcine kidney : 0.8 units/mg, Sigma), L- and D-amino acids (Sigma), hydroxyethylcellulose (HEC; Fluka), polyethylenimine (PEI; Sigma-Aldrich) were used. The substrate for the printed sensors was 250 μm thick polyester sheet (Cadillac Plastic Ltd., Swindon, U.K.). The basal tracks and bases of the three electrodes were printed using MCA 45R carbon ink (MCA Services Ltd., Melbourne, Cambs., U.K.). For the enzyme sensor, the electrocatalytic material (aqueous based) for the circular WE was made from 1 part MCA4A rhodinated carbon powder and 4 parts of 2% (w/v) HEC in phosphate buffer (Sigma-Aldrich) con-

taining 1% (w/v) PEI. However, the WE for the dual potential electrode was made from only MCA4A an HEC in the above proportion. The material for the reference electrode was 15% silver chloride in silver paste (MCA) for both types. To protect the underlying basal tracks from solution, an epoxy-based protective coating ink 242-SB (Agmet ESL Ltd. U.K.) was deposited over areas of the electrodes that were not exposed to sample, leaving tracks exposed at the proximal end in order to make electrical connection with the instrument.

trodes. The black area represents the screen opening, through which ink will pass and make an identical print. The ash colour represents the blocked part of the screen, i.e. no ink will pass through. The basal track was first made with carbon ink using screen *a* (Fig. 2). The impression of the reference electrode was then made with Ag/AgCl ink on the same substrate using screen *b*. The MCA4a ink with additives was used to print the working electrode on the substrate with screen *c*. Finally, the nonconducting polymer coating was made using screen *d*. The final electrode thus looked like *d* in Fig. 2. Heat treatment of the electrodes was carried out for 2 h at 120°.

Preparation of enzyme electrode : An aliquot (10 μl) of a mixture of both L- and D-amino acid oxidases (20 mU of L-AAO and 25 mU of D-AAO per electrode) in 2% glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (PB), pH 7.8 was deposited on the WE of the screen-printed sensor and kept overnight at 4°. The dried electrodes were washed with buffer and stored at 4° until further use. This system worked at very low enzyme concentration and did not require co-immobilisation of another enzyme (e.g. HRP) to amplify the response. The working potential of +400 mV vs Ag/

AgCl was chosen to minimise the electrochemical interference due to oxidation of easily oxidisable compounds, which might be present in the analyte. The printed electrodes described above were used as dual-step potential electrodes. Immunodyne ABC membranes were cut into circular discs (1.1 cm dia) and soaked in concentrated (100 mg in 4 ml) protease solution in 0.05 M phosphate buffer, pH 7 for 30 min. These were dried at room temperature for 2 h. The remaining active sites of the membrane were washed and blocked by 50 mM TES buffer, pH 7.8 containing 3 mM CaCl_2 for 2 h in an orbital shaker at 100 rpm.

Electrochemical measurement :

Enzyme electrode : The protease pads were first soaked with 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.8 and the dust sample was wiped in. The sensor was connected to a Autolab Electrochemical analyser (Ecochemie, Utrecht, The Netherlands) and the pad, i.e. the membrane placed on the electrode surface. This ensured contact among the three electrodes. The working electrode was poised at 400 mV potential, 40 μl of the analyte deposited on the protease pad and the response was noted after 4 min using the General Purpose Electrochemical Software (GPES3) supplied by Ecochemie.

Dual potential electrode : Bromine was previously generated by application of appropriate voltage across the electrode from a potassium bromide buffer electrolyte. These sensors are novel in nature since detection may be done on site using a hand held meter with only 40 μl of phosphate or potassium bromide buffer. Whatman filter paper (1.1 cm dia) was soaked into freshly prepared 0.25 M KBr in so-

dium phosphate buffer, pH 5.0. An aliquot (40 μl) of the same buffer was deposited on the filter paper and the working electrode was poised at high potential (1–1.5 V) for 2 min and at lower potential for 2 more min. During the generation step, the following reaction occurs at the electrode surface : $2 \text{Br}^- = \text{Br}_2 + 2e^-$. Due to consumption of Br in the second stage, the reaction occurred in the forward direction releasing more electrons, and hence higher current.

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